

حضرت صوفی محمد برکت علیؒ کی علمی اور سماجی خدمات ایک مطالعہ

A Study of the Scholarly and Social Services of Hazrat Sufi Muhammad Barkat Ali

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Abstract

Sufi Muhammad Barkat Ali (1911–1997) was a renowned saint, mystic, and reformer of the 20th century, whose life, character, and teachings profoundly influenced hundreds of thousands of individuals. Originating from central Punjab and initially serving in the British Army, he rose to a spiritual stature rarely witnessed in modern times. His simplicity, eloquent language, and profound spiritual insight attracted followers from distant regions, forming a community marked by unique ethics, lifestyle, and thought. These followers lived harmoniously with themselves, others, and society at large. Sufi Barkat Ali was a steadfast adherent of Islamic teachings (Shariah), passionately emphasizing the practice of Qur'anic principles. His deep love for the Qur'an culminated in the establishment of the Qur'an Mehal, a symbol of devotion and a centre for authentic Islamic learning. Central to his message was the collective remembrance of Allah (Zikr), which he stressed as an essential means of spiritual connection and universal harmony. He authored numerous works, particularly focusing on the Beautiful Names of Allah and Words of Wisdom, which continue to serve as beacons of hope, spirituality, and moral guidance. Although Sufi Muhammad Barkat Ali has departed from this world, his spiritual legacy continues to illuminate the lives of millions globally.

Keywords: Sufi Muhammad Barkat Ali, Islamic Mysticism, Qur'an Mehal, Zikr, Spiritual Reformation, Islamic Teachings, Names of Allah, Words of Wisdom, Community Development, Modern Sufism.

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